

A mononuclear organoruthenium complex of a polydentate thiosemicarbazone ligand and its utilization as a building block for the synthesis of heterodinuclear Ru-Pd and Ru-Pt complexes

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Abstract : Reaction of 2,6-diacetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone with $[\text{Ru}(\text{CO})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ in refluxing ethanol affords a mononuclear ruthenium complex [Ru], in which the thiosemicarbazone is coordinated to ruthenium as dianionic CNS-donor, along with two triphenylphosphines and a carbonyl. Using the unutilized donor atoms in the free wing of the thiosemicarbazone in the [Ru] complex two hetero-bimetallic [Ru-Pd] and [Ru-Pt] complexes have been synthesized via reaction of the [Ru] complex with $[\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ respectively. Structures of the [Ru] and [Ru-Pt] complexes have been determined by X-ray crystallography. Structure of the [Ru-Pd] complex has been optimized by DFT method. The free wing of the thiosemicarbazone in the [Ru] complex is utilized in binding to the second metal center in dianionic CNS-mode in the [Ru-Pd] and [Ru-Pt] complexes, and a triphenylphosphine has occupied the fourth coordination site on the second metal center. All the three complexes show characteristic IR and ^1H NMR spectra. They also display intense absorptions in the visible and ultraviolet regions.

Keywords : 2,6-Diacetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone, Ru complex, Ru-Pd and Ru-Pt complexes, syntheses, structures, spectral properties.

Introduction

There has been considerable current attention in the chemistry of thiosemicarbazone complexes of transition metal ions, largely because of their bioinorganic relevance¹. Studies on the binding of thiosemicarbazone ligands of different types to selected transition metal ions, with an aim to develop new and interesting complexes, are therefore of significant importance. However, we have been exploring the chemistry of transition metal complexes of thiosemicarbazones, mainly because of the variable binding mode displayed by these ligands in their complexes, and the present work has originated out of this exploration². For the present study we have selected 2,6-diacetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (abbreviated as L) as the principal ligand and ruthenium as the metal center. The chemistry of ruthenium is being heavily explored³, owing to the interesting redox, photochemical and catalytic properties exhibited by the complexes of this metal, and we have also been interested in the chemistry of ruthenium in different coordination environments^{2a-d,j,l,o,4}. The selected thiosemicarbazone (L) has two identical wings

on either side of the central pyridine ring, containing nitrogen and sulfur as donor atoms. Hence this ligand has the potential to behave as a dianionic polydentate ligand, via dissociation of the two acidic protons, and coordinate to metal center(s) in several possible modes. In order to study the interaction of this chosen thiosemicarbazone (L) with ruthenium, $[\text{Ru}(\text{CO})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ has been selected as the source of ruthenium, primarily because of

its demonstrated ability to undergo facile reaction with ligands of different types to yield interesting mixed-ligand complexes^{4a,f,g,i-1}. The main objective of the undertaken study has been to scrutinize how the thiosemicarbazone ligand (L) interacts with the metal center in $[\text{Ru}(\text{CO})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$, and binds to it. Reaction of the

chosen thiosemicarbazone (**L**) with $[\text{Ru}(\text{CO})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ has indeed afforded an interesting mononuclear complex, in which the thiosemicarbazone displays a rather unexpected mode of binding. Utilizing this ruthenium complex as a building block, two heterodinuclear Ru-Pd and Ru-Pt complexes have been synthesized. Herein we describe the chemistry of these three complexes, with special reference to their formation, structure and spectral properties.

Experimental

Materials :

Ruthenium trichloride, palladium chloride and chloroplatinic acid were purchased from Arora Matthey, Kolkata, India. Triphenylphosphine was obtained from S.D. Fine-Chem Limited. $[\text{Ru}(\text{CO})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ were prepared by following reported methods⁵. Thiosemicarbazide was procured from SRL, and 2,6-diacetylpyridine was purchased from Aldrich. The thiosemicarbazone ligand (**L**) was prepared by reacting thiosemicarbazide with 2,6-diacetylpyridine in 2 : 1 mole ratio in hot 1 : 1 ethanol-water mixture. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade commercial materials and were used as received.

Syntheses of complexes :

[Ru] complex : 2,6-Diacetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (42 mg, 0.14 mmol) was dissolved in warm ethanol (40 mL), and then $[\text{Ru}(\text{CO})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ (100 mg, 0.14 mmol) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 12 h to yield an orange solution. The solvent was then evaporated and the solid mass, thus obtained, was subjected to purification by thin layer chromatography on a silica plate. With 1 : 5 acetonitrile-benzene as the eluant, an orange band separated, which was extracted with acetonitrile. Evaporation of the acetonitrile extract gave complex **[Ru]** as an orange crystalline solid. Yield : 65%; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{41}\text{N}_7\text{O}_1\text{P}_2\text{S}_2\text{Ru}$: C, 60.12; H, 4.28; N, 10.23. Found : C, 60.83; H, 4.25; N, 10.16%; $^1\text{H NMR}^6$: 2.01 (s, CH_3), 2.15 (s, CH_3), 4.29 (s, NH_2), 4.42 (s, NH_2), 6.09 (1H, d, J 7.5), 6.39 (1H, d, J 7.5), 7.11–7.66 (2PPh₃ + NH)*; IR : 1919, 1595, 1434, 1382, 1308, 1244, 1173, 1091, 1013, 827, 745, 696, 521 cm^{-1} .

[Ru-Pd] complex : Complex **[Ru]** (137 mg, 0.14 mmol) was dissolved in warm ethanol (40 mL), and then

$[\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ (100 mg, 0.14 mmol) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 6 h to yield an orange solution. The solvent was then evaporated and the solid mass, thus obtained, was subjected to purification by thin layer chromatography on a silica plate. With 1 : 5 acetonitrile-benzene as the eluant, an orange band separated, which was extracted with acetonitrile. Evaporation of the acetonitrile extract gave complex **[Ru-Pd]** as an orange crystalline solid. Yield : 58%; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{66}\text{H}_{56}\text{N}_7\text{O}_1\text{P}_3\text{S}_2\text{RuPd}$: C, 59.71; H, 4.22; N, 7.39. Found : C, 60.02; H, 4.14; N, 7.42%; $^1\text{H NMR}$: 2.15 (s, CH_3), 2.19 (s, CH_3), 4.39 (s, NH_2), 4.46 (s, NH_2), 6.24 (s, 1H), 7.10–7.78 (3PPh₃)*; IR : 1919, 1680, 1586, 1531, 1482, 1434, 1384, 1356, 1300, 1233, 1162, 1091, 1009, 838, 748, 692, 521 cm^{-1} .

[Ru-Pt] complex : This complex was synthesized by following the same above procedure using $[\text{Pt}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ instead of $[\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$. Yield : 55%; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{66}\text{H}_{56}\text{N}_7\text{O}_1\text{P}_3\text{S}_2\text{RuPt}$: C, 55.97; H, 3.96; N, 6.93. Found : C, 56.15; H, 3.91; N, 6.86%; $^1\text{H NMR}$: 2.17 (s, CH_3), 2.20 (s, CH_3), 4.37 (s, NH_2), 4.44 (s, NH_2), 6.24 (1H, s), 7.12–7.83 (3PPh₃)*; IR : 1917, 1681, 1584, 1531, 1483, 1434, 1386, 1356, 1297, 1233, 1166, 1091, 1009, 838, 745, 693, 520 cm^{-1} .

Physical measurements :

Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured using a Sherwood MK-1 balance. $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra recorded in CDCl_3 solution on a Bruker Avance DPX 300 NMR spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. IR spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum two spectrometer with samples prepared as KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-570 spectrophotometer.

X-Ray crystallography :

Single crystals of the **[Ru]** and **[Ru-Pt]** complexes were obtained by slow evaporation of solvent from solutions of the complexes in acetonitrile. Selected crystal data and data collection parameters are given in Table 1. Data were collected on a Bruker SMART CCD diffractometer using graphite monochromated $\text{MoK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). X-Ray data reduction, structure solution and refinement were done using SHELXS-97 and SHELXL-97 programs⁷. The structures were solved by the direct methods.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for the [Ru] and [Ru-Pt] complexes

Empirical formula	C ₅₀ H ₄₆ N ₈ OP ₂ S ₂ Ru	C ₆₆ H ₅₆ N ₇ OP ₃ S ₂ PtRu
Formula mass	1002.10	1416.38
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Triclinic
Space group	P2 ₁ /n	P $\bar{1}$
<i>a</i> (Å)	10.878(9)	13.714(2)
<i>b</i> (Å)	14.159(12)	13.751(2)
<i>c</i> (Å)	31.37(3)	16.380(3)
α (deg)	90	74.701(2)
β (deg)	95.711(14)	85.054(2)
γ (deg)	90	84.562(3)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	4808(7)	2960.1(8)
<i>Z</i>	4	2
<i>D</i> _{Calcd.} (mg m ⁻³)	1.384	1.589
<i>F</i> (000)	2064	1416
Crystal size (mm)	0.22 × 0.15 × 0.11	0.19 × 0.18 × 0.15
<i>T</i> (K)	298	298
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.526	2.817
<i>R</i> ₁ ^a	0.0712	0.0560
<i>wR</i> ₂ ^b	0.2547	0.1699
GOF ^c	0.78	0.85

$$^a R_1 = \frac{\sum \|F_o\| - |F_c|}{\sum \|F_o\|}$$

$$^b wR_2 = \left[\frac{\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2]}{\sum [w(F_o^2)^2]} \right]^{1/2}$$

$$^c \text{GOF} = \left[\frac{\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)]}{(M - N)} \right]^{1/2}, \text{ where } M \text{ is the number of reflections and } N \text{ is the number of parameters refined.}$$

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

As delineated in the introduction, the primary aim of the present work has been to study the interaction between 2,6-diacetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (L) and [Ru(CO)₂(PPh₃)₂Cl₂] and find out the binding mode of the chosen thiosemicarbazone to ruthenium. Reaction of 2,6-diacetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone with [Ru(CO)₂(PPh₃)₂Cl₂] proceed smoothly in refluxing ethanol to yield an orange crystalline solid in good yield, henceforth referred to as the [Ru] complex. Preliminary characterization (microanalytical, IR and NMR) data on this complex indicate the formation of a mononuclear ruthenium complex containing triphenylphosphine and carbonyl ligands. In order to authenticate the composition of this complex, as well as to find out coordination mode of the chosen thiosemicarbazone in it, structure of this complex has been determined by X-ray crystallography. The structure is shown in Fig. 1 and some relevant bond parameters are listed in Table 2. The structure shows

Fig. 1. (a) Crystal structure of the [Ru] complex (hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity) and, (b) view of the equatorial plane with atom numbering scheme.

Table 2. Selected bond distances and bond angles for the [Ru], [Ru-Pt] and [Ru-Pd] complexes^a

[Ru]			
Bond distances (Å)			
Ru(1)-P(1)	2.379(3)	C(1)-N(2)	1.311(11)
Ru(1)-P(2)	2.387(3)	N(2)-N(1)	1.387(8)
Ru(1)-S(1)	2.437(3)	N(1)-C(2)	1.300(11)
Ru(1)-N(1)	2.096(6)	C(9)-N(5)	1.280(12)
Ru(1)-C(5)	2.072(8)	N(5)-N(6)	1.360(11)
Ru(1)-C(12)	1.831(8)	N(6)-C(11)	1.347(12)
C(12)-O(1)	1.166(11)	C(11)-S(2)	1.647(10)
C(1)-S(1)	1.735(9)	C(11)-N(7)	1.329(14)
C(1)-N(3)	1.351(11)		
Bond angles (deg)			
P(1)-Ru(1)-P(2)	176.81(7)	S(1)-Ru(1)-N(1)	79.83(17)
S(1)-Ru(1)-C(5)	158.0(2)	N(1)-Ru(1)-C(5)	78.3(3)
N(1)-Ru(1)-C(12)	176.7(3)		

Table-2 (contd.)

[Ru-Pt]			
Bond distances (Å)			
Ru(1)-P(1)	2.360(3)	Pt(1)-P(3)	2.236(3)
Ru(1)-P(2)	2.423(3)	Pt(1)-S(2)	2.339(3)
Ru(1)-S(1)	2.462(3)	Pt(1)-N(5)	2.034(7)
Ru(1)-N(1)	2.099(7)	Pt(1)-C(7)	2.048(9)
Ru(1)-C(5)	2.093(8)	Ru(1)-Pt(1)	6.382(13)
Ru(1)-C(12)	1.830(10)		
C(1)-S(1)	1.734(10)	C(11)-S(2)	1.758(10)
C(1)-N(3)	1.357(12)	C(11)-N(7)	1.351(14)
C(1)-N(2)	1.315(13)	C(11)-N(6)	1.292(12)
N(2)-N(1)	1.394(9)	N(6)-N(5)	1.395(11)
N(1)-C(2)	1.299(11)	N(5)-C(9)	1.306(12)
C(12)-O(1)	1.184(12)		
Bond angles (deg)			
P(1)-Ru(1)-P(2)	171.88(9)	P(3)-Pt(1)-N(5)	174.2(2)
S(1)-Ru(1)-C(5)	157.9(2)	C(7)-Pt(1)-S(2)	162.6(3)
N(1)-Ru(1)-C(12)	177.2(3)	C(7)-Pt(1)-N(5)	80.9(3)
S(1)-Ru(1)-N(1)	78.98(19)	N(5)-Pt(1)-S(2)	82.0(2)
N(1)-Ru(1)-C(5)	79.0(3)		
Ru(1)-C(12)-O(1)	178.2(9)		
[Ru-Pd]			
Bond distances (Å)			
Ru(2)-P(5)	2.358	Pd(1)-P(7)	2.232
Ru(2)-P(6)	2.427	Pd(1)-S(4)	2.338
Ru(2)-S(3)	2.452	Pd(1)-N(91)	1.995
Ru(2)-N(10)	2.129	Pd(1)-C(8)	2.119
Ru(2)-C(85)	2.105	Ru(2)-Pd(1)	6.388
Ru(2)-C(20)	1.839		
C(12)-S(3)	1.800	C(106)-S(4)	1.681
C(12)-N(87)	1.295	C(106)-N(93)	1.334
C(12)-N(11)	1.348	C(106)-N(92)	1.405
N(11)-N(10)	1.378	N(92)-N(91)	1.478
N(10)-C(96)	1.274	N(91)-C(101)	1.318
C(20)-O(21)	1.178		
Bond angles (deg)			
P(5)-Ru(2)-P(6)	171.72	P(7)-Pd(1)-N(91)	175.38
S(3)-Ru(2)-C(85)	160.21	C(8)-Pd(1)-S(4)	161.93
N(10)-Ru(2)-C(20)	177.40	C(8)-Pd(1)-N(91)	79.79
S(3)-Ru(2)-N(10)	79.01	N(91)-Pd(1)-S(4)	82.37
N(10)-Ru(2)-C(85)	81.32		
Ru(2)-C(20)-O(21)	176.75		

^aData for the [Ru] and [Ru-Pt] complexes are from crystal structures, and those for the [Ru-Pd] complex are from DFT-optimized structure.

that the chosen thiosemicarbazone (**L**) is coordinated to ruthenium as a tridentate CNS-donor (as in **I**) utilizing only one of its two wings. It is interesting to note that in

I

spite of having the pyridine nitrogen as a potential donor atom, the thiosemicarbazone ligand (**L**) has not used it for complexation, instead, it has undergone a rather unexpected C-H bond activation during its binding to the metal center. Two triphenylphosphines and a carbonyl are also coordinated to ruthenium. The carbonyl is sharing the same equatorial plane with the CNS-coordinated ligand, and it is *trans* to the ruthenium-bound nitrogen. The two triphenylphosphines have taken up the two remaining axial positions on the metal center, and hence they are mutually *trans*. The observed bond parameters around ruthenium are all quite normal, and so are those within the coordinated thiosemicarbazone ligand^{2a-d,j,l,o}. In this [Ru] complex ruthenium is thus nested in a C₂NP₂S coordination sphere, which is distorted significantly from ideal octahedral geometry, as reflected in the bond parameters around the metal center.

Presence of several unutilized donor atoms in the free wing of the thiosemicarbazone ligand in the [Ru] complex indicates possibility of incorporating a second metal center in this wing and thereby generating interesting hetero-bimetallic complexes. In order to explore this possibility reactions of the [Ru] complex have been carried out with [Pd(PPh₃)₂Cl₂] and [Pt(PPh₃)₂Cl₂] in refluxing ethanol, which have afforded two new complexes, henceforth referred to as the [Ru-Pd] and [Ru-Pt] complexes respectively, in decent yields. Structure of the [Ru-Pt] complex has been determined by X-ray crystallography. The structure (Fig. 2) clearly shows that the free wing of the thiosemicarbazone in the [Ru] complex is indeed utilized in binding to platinum, again in a rather unexpected CNS-mode (as in II, M = Pt) in this [Ru-Pt] complex. A triphenylphosphine has fulfilled the fourth coordination site on platinum. The bond parameters around ruthenium

Fig. 2. (a) Crystal structure of the [Ru-Pt] complex and, (b) view of the equatorial plane with atom numbering scheme. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

in this [Ru-Pt] complex are found to be comparable to those in the [Ru] complex (Table 2). The metrical parameters around platinum are also found to be usual^{2h,q}. This structural characterization of this [Ru-Pt] complex thus shows that the free wing of the thiosemicarbazone ligand in the [Ru] complex can be successfully utilized for the synthesis of hetero-bimetallic complex. Structural characterization of the [Ru-Pd] complex by X-ray crystallography has not been possible, as single crystals of this complex could not be grown. However, its structure has

II

been geometrically optimized by density functional theory (DFT) method using the Gaussian 03 (B3LYP/SDD-6-31G) package⁸, where phenyl rings of the triphenylphosphines have been replaced by hydrogens for simpli-

ppm. The two expected doublets from the central pyridine fragment have been located at 6.09 and 6.39 ppm. Signals from the coordinated triphenylphosphines have appeared as broad peaks within 7.11–7.66 ppm, and the NH signal is probably buried somewhere under the PPh₃ peaks. ¹H NMR spectra of the [Ru-Pd] and [Ru-Pt] complexes are qualitatively very similar to that of the [Ru] complex, except that only a singlet is observed from the central pyridine fragment at 6.24 ppm, which corresponds well with the mode of binding (II) of the thiosemicarbazone ligand in these two hetero-bimetallic complexes.

Infrared spectra of the [Ru], [Ru-Pd] and [Ru-Pt] complexes show many bands of different intensities in the 400–4000 cm⁻¹ region. No attempt has been made to assign each individual band to a specific vibration. However, a strong band around 1919 cm⁻¹, observed in all the three complexes, is attributed to the coordinated carbonyl. Three strong bands, displayed near 745, 694 and 520 cm⁻¹ by all the complexes, are due to the coordinated PPh₃ ligands. Besides, comparison of the spectrum of the [Ru] complex with that of the [Ru(CO)₂(PPh₃)₂Cl₂] complex shows that several new bands (e.g. at 1595, 1308 and 1091 cm⁻¹) are present in the spectrum of the [Ru] complex, which are attributable to the coordinated thiosemicarbazone ligand in it. Similar bands, due to the coordinated thiosemicarbazone ligand, are also found in the [Ru-Pd] and [Ru-Pt] complexes near 1585, 1300 and 1091 cm⁻¹, which are absent in the spectra of the [M(PPh₃)₂Cl₂] (M = Pd, Pt) complexes. The ¹H NMR and IR spectral data of the [Ru], [Ru-Pd] and [Ru-Pt] complexes are therefore consistent with their composition.

The [Ru], [Ru-Pd] and [Ru-Pt] complexes are found to be readily soluble in dichloromethane, chloroform, acetonitrile, etc., producing bright yellow solutions. Electronic spectra of these complexes have been recorded in acetonitrile solution. Each complex shows several intense absorptions in the visible and ultraviolet regions. Spectral data are presented in Table 3. All the three complexes exhibit similar spectral features. The absorptions in the ultraviolet region are attributable to transitions within the ligand orbitals. The intense absorption displayed by the [Ru]₂ complex at 492 nm is assignable to a metal-to-ligand charge transfer transition. The same transition is also observed in the bimetallic [Ru-Pd] and [Ru-Pt] com-

Table 3. Electronic spectral data^a

Complex	λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)
[Ru]	492 (1600), 400 (5100), 336 ^b (9700), 304 ^b (44500), 276 (11900)
[Ru-Pd]	488 (2000), 390 (4200), 334 ^b (6250), 274 (9800)
[Ru-Pt]	480 (2050), 390 ^b (3600), 350 (6250), 278 ^b (18000)

^aIn acetonitrile solution.

^bShoulder.

plexes at 488 nm and 480 nm, respectively. Inclusion of palladium or platinum as the second metal center is thus found to be associated with no diagnostic change in the spectral properties.

Conclusion

The present study shows that 2,6-diacetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (**L**) can readily react with [Ru(CO)₂(PPh₃)₂Cl₂] and bind to the metal center in a rather unexpected CNS-mode (as in I) affording a mononuclear [Ru] complex. This study also demonstrates that, by virtue of having unutilized donor sites in the free wing of the ruthenium-bound thiosemicarbazone, this organoruthenium [Ru] complex can serve as an efficient building block for the preparation of interesting bimetallic complexes, which has been realized in the syntheses of two hetero-dinuclear [Ru-Pd] and [Ru-Pt] complexes. Further studies on the utilization of this [Ru] complex for the preparation of bimetallic complexes of other types are currently underway.

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Appendix A

Supplementary data :

Crystallographic data of the [Ru-Pt] and [Ru] complexes have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC numbers 928689 and 928690.

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